

Trafficking of Women and Human Rights in the Legal Perspective of Present Era and Beyond

Rashmi Mishra¹ & J.S.P. Srivastava²

1. Research Scholar, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee
2. Professor & Dean, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee

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Abstract

Human trafficking is explicitly banned by the Indian Constitution. Article 23 of the Fundamental Rights section forbids "traffic in human beings and other similar forms of forced labour." Although "trafficking" lacks a precise definition, it generally refers to the movement or transportation of individuals through deceit or coercion, leading to their exploitation and eventual commercialization. Traffickers exploit the vulnerabilities of their victims, who are then subjected to abuse by recruiters, transporters, sellers, buyers, end-users, and the traffickers themselves. The rise of globalization has caused a dramatic increase in trafficking. Factors such as organized crime, high profits with minimal risk, and low prioritization by law enforcement exacerbate the issue. Human trafficking generates profits comparable to those from drug and weapon trafficking. The trafficking of women and children is particularly egregious and represents one of the most severe violations of human rights. Despite its complexity, the legal community, academia, and civil society have often overlooked the issue. While often equated with prostitution, human trafficking encompasses various forms, including transnational sexual exploitation. Unlike smuggling, trafficking typically involves coercion, particularly of young, impoverished girls. Many trafficked women are aware they will be traveling but are deceived about the nature of the forced labor they will perform, their inability to leave, and the conditions they will endure. This paper argues for increased focus on the root causes and related crimes of human trafficking, which threaten the security of trafficked individuals in India. It also suggests preventive measures to address and mitigate the problem.

Key words: Constitution, Fundamental Rights, trafficking, human rights, globalization, sexual exploitation.

Introduction

Human trafficking of women and girls typically involves prostitution, pornography, forced labor (including domestic and commercial agricultural work), arranged marriages, or selling women as brides, as well as recruitment for hostilities and related activities like sexual services, portage, and household duties during conflicts. The experiences of trafficked women and girls differ from those of men and boys, often with disproportionately severe impacts on the former. Men, when trafficked, frequently face challenges accessing victim assistance programs. This disparity underscores the need to integrate gender equality principles into the development and implementation of anti-trafficking policies and initiatives. Despite widespread acknowledgment by governmental and human rights organizations that trafficking of women is a serious human rights violation requiring urgent action, the complex and pervasive nature of human trafficking makes prosecuting and punishing traffickers exceedingly difficult.

The trafficking of women has deep historical roots, predating the establishment of civilizations. In ancient times, female slaves were highly valued for their reproductive abilities and roles as concubines or prostitutes. The Indian Penal Code's recently enacted Section 370 prohibits human

trafficking for physical or sexual exploitation, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude, and the forced removal of organs. This clause has led to the registration of cases involving various contemporary slavery practices. Since ratifying the Palermo Protocol and amending its Penal Code, India has outlawed trafficking for sexual exploitation. The Immoral Traffic in Persons Act of 1956 also criminalizes procuring, coercing, or taking someone for prostitution. The Protection of Children from Sexual Offenses Act of 2012 prohibits several sexual offenses against minors under the age of 18.

Human trafficking includes multiple elements such as sex trafficking, labor trafficking, and organ trafficking. "Sex trafficking" refers to human trafficking for prostitution. Globally, 50% of trafficking victims are minors under 18, and 70% are women. The annual revenues from human trafficking are estimated at \$7 billion, with between 700,000 and four million women and children trafficked each year. The demand for cheap labor in households, factories, the sex industry, and agriculture drives human trafficking. Globalization has facilitated trade between human traffickers, who severely exploit and abuse these women in forced sex work. These women are highly vulnerable to HIV infection.

Persistent poverty and a lack of job opportunities have led more women to enter the sex industry voluntarily. Trafficking is not only an extreme human rights violation but also an organized criminal activity that raises social justice, economic empowerment, and extreme commercial sexual exploitation issues. It presents a multifaceted and transnational challenge, violating the rights and dignity of individuals and causing immense suffering. Human trafficking infringes on the rights to life, dignity, privacy, security, health, education, and grievance redress.

Human Rights and Indian Constitution

Human Rights (HR) have traditionally been defined as the "basic moral guarantees that individuals possess simply because they are human". These rights are "universally applicable, reflecting the essential conditions necessary for every person to lead a fulfilling life". "This philosophy has been articulated in various declarations and agreements, beginning with the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, followed by the 1954 European Convention on Human Rights, and the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. These documents collectively form the foundation of a moral philosophy focused on Human Rights (HR). According to Jack Donnelly, human rights are the new standard of civilization, fundamental and inalienable."

The emphasis on human dignity is a common thread in international accords like the United Nations Charter, the UDHR, and the Indian Constitution. The Indian Constitution's preamble highlights the guarantee of individual dignity as one of its core values. Drafted around the same time as the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights (HR)", the Indian Constitution reflects many of its principles. For instance, "Articles 23 of Part III of the Indian Constitution and Articles 2-21 of the UDHR share similarities". Additionally, "Part IV of the Indian Constitution, which includes Directive Principles of State Policy (Articles 38, 39A, 41, etc.), corresponds to Articles 22-28 of the UDHR."

The Indian Constitution, therefore, provides extensive provisions for protecting and promoting human rights, with the Indian Supreme Court playing a crucial role in upholding these fundamental freedoms. The importance of fundamental rights is underscored by their accessibility to both citizens and non-citizens, demonstrating the enduring relevance of these rights in the contemporary world.

Understanding Human Rights

According to the Oxford Dictionary, "trafficking" means "dealing in something, especially illegally. This includes terms like drug trafficking, arms trafficking, and human trafficking". Human trafficking is defined as "the criminal practice of exploiting individuals by treating them as commodities for profit, subjecting them to long-term exploitation". Alongside narcotics and weapons, human trafficking is now one of the three most profitable types of organized crime. The severity of human rights violations in human trafficking is both inconceivable and unimaginable, causing this crime to

reach alarming levels. Unfortunately, public awareness of this crime is minimal, largely due to its covert and secretive nature. The complexity of the issue also makes it difficult to obtain consensus statistics, as various organizations provide differing figures. Human trafficking is often referred to as modern-day slavery.

Women Trafficking In India

Women and girls from Bangladesh and Nepal are trafficked to India for commercial sexual exploitation. Additionally, children from Nepal are brought to India to work as forced labor in circuses. Indian women are trafficked to the Middle East for commercial sexual exploitation. Every year, many Indians voluntarily migrate to the Middle East and Europe seeking employment as low-skilled laborers and domestic servants. Some of these workers become vulnerable to exploitation by unscrupulous employers who subject them to involuntary servitude, such as non-payment of wages, restricted movement, unlawful withholding of passports, and physical or sexual abuse. Others are deceived by fraudulent recruitment practices that lead directly to forced labor and debt bondage.

A recent poll conducted in India among prostitutes identified common reasons for entering the profession, which are shared by women in other countries as well. These reasons, listed in order of importance, include unemployment and poverty, inadequate reintegration services, lack of options, stigma and negative social attitudes, family pressure and expectations, and resignation to their lifestyle. In India, two primary laws specifically address prostitution and trafficking.

- The Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act of 1956 (SITA) and
- The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act of 1986 (ITPA), colloquially called PITA, an amendment to SITA.

While neither legislation explicitly prohibits prostitution, both laws ban soliciting and commercialized vice. However, the enforcement of SITA (Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act) has various issues. One major problem is the disparity in penalties based on gender: a pimp faces three months in jail, while a prostitute—always defined as a woman under SITA—can be imprisoned for up to a year for soliciting. SITA only allowed for the prosecution of individuals who were not prostitutes if they had "knowingly" or "willingly" forced women into prostitution. This loophole enabled procurers, madams, pimps, and brothel owners to claim ignorance and avoid prosecution. Moreover, clients were not considered offenders under SITA and were not subject to its penalties. SITA primarily targeted street prostitution, ignoring activities that occurred behind closed doors, thereby allowing brothels to flourish.

A recent survey highlights that women from various districts in India are trafficked to other nations where they are bought and sold. These women and girls come from places like Murshidabad and 24 Parganas in West Bengal; Maharajgunj in Uttar Pradesh; Dholpur, Alwar, and Tonk in Rajasthan; Mangalore; Dindigal, Madurai, Tiruchirapalli, and Chengalpattu in Tamil Nadu; Gaya, Kishanganj, Patna, Katihar, Purnea, Araria, and Madhubani in Bihar; and Gulbarga and Raichur in Karnataka. They are trafficked to countries such as Thailand, Kenya, South Africa, Bahrain, Dubai, Oman, Britain, South Korea, and the Philippines. These women endure extreme exploitation and abuse while being forced to work as sex workers, making them highly susceptible to HIV infection.

Persistent poverty and a lack of job opportunities have led to an increase in women voluntarily entering the sex industry. Trafficking for commercial or non-commercial sexual exploitation is a complex international issue involving organized crime, severe human rights violations, and social justice and economic empowerment concerns. The trafficking of women and children gravely violates their rights and dignity, resulting in immense suffering. This crime infringes upon the rights to life, dignity, privacy, security, health, education, and grievance resolution.

Causes and Modes of Trafficking in India:

There are various factors that contribute to human trafficking, especially involving women and children. These factors can be categorized into two main types: push factors and pull factors:

The push factors include poor socioeconomic conditions in many families, poverty combined with frequent natural disasters like floods that leave people destitute, lack of education, skills, and job opportunities for women and their families in rural areas, and ignorance about the activities of human traffickers. Additionally, the need to raise money for dowries often “forces daughters to seek work in distant places, and issues such as dysfunctional families, domestic violence against women, and the low status of girl children exacerbate the situation”. Case studies show that extreme poverty and other forms of deprivation not only make people vulnerable to traffickers but also motivate trafficking. Due to a lack of alternatives, prostitutes often become involved with traffickers and eventually follow in their footsteps after escaping abusive environments.

Pull factors include the demand for young girls for marriage in different regions, the need for cheap and underage labor in sweatshops, the rising demand for young children for adoption, the lure of easy money and lucrative job opportunities in big cities, and the promise of better pay and a more comfortable life from traffickers and agents. The growing sex industry also increases demand for women, particularly in military areas like Kashmir in India. Beliefs that sex with a virgin cures HIV-AIDS and impotence, or reduces men's risk of contracting the disease, have also fuelled the demand for young girls for sexual exploitation. Internal trafficking has been further supported by the widespread practice of female feticide in northern states like Haryana and Punjab, creating a low female-to-male ratio and a shortage of women. Traffickers exploit this by recruiting young women from remote regions like “Assam and Orissa”, misleading “their families into believing they are entering into marriage, and then forcing them into prostitution.”

Due to globalization, India is experiencing significant shifts in its labor, political, economic, and demographic patterns. The high population growth and increasing demand for cheap labor drive both legal and illegal migration. “Young girls and women from Bangladesh and Nepal” often end up in Indian brothels. Initially, this begins as illegal migration but turns into trafficking, especially during times of hardship. Migration is driven by the supply & demand dynamics in “both the sending and receiving countries. Structural inequality, poverty, illiteracy, and lack of livelihood opportunities fuel the supply side, while the demand side is driven by the need for cheap labor in destination countries. People from poorer countries like Bangladesh and Nepal are particularly vulnerable to exploitation and trafficking to neighboring India.”

A study by ESCAP on sexually exploited children and youth in South Asia reveals that young girls from certain rural areas of Bangladesh, India, and Nepal are trafficked for marriage and then sold into prostitution (Shamim, 2010). Poor families in India also face significant challenges due to their limited ability to communicate outside their local area, with many being illiterate and reliant on others to make phone calls or send letters. Legal guardians often fail to support the victims, and it is commonly alleged that victims receive more harassment from police than criminals do. These factors leave economically and socially marginalized groups more vulnerable to human trafficking and contribute to high rates of re-trafficking.

Globalization has also fueled the growth of the travel and entertainment industries, leading to the rapid expansion of sex-related industries like sex tourism. The demanding conditions in the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sector and the increasing number of men moving to cities have also contributed to the rising demand for commercial sex in urban areas. There is a clear connection between child marriage and human trafficking. Traffickers often use child marriage to transport young girls from one place to another. In traditional rural communities, single women are viewed negatively, and parents feel embarrassed if they cannot arrange their daughter's marriage. This pressure makes it difficult for parents to refuse marriage proposals from traffickers, who sometimes offer monetary rewards ranging from Rs. 1000 to Rs. 5000, excluding dowry. The girls are then sold and resold after marriage until they reach their final destination.

In addition to child marriage, there are various forms of child trafficking, including fake marriages, fraudulent recruitment, kidnapping, transporting children with guardians' consent, adopting children, and exploiting impoverished families living in wealthier cities.

Reason for Increased Women/Young Girls Trafficking in India

The following are the causes of the rise in India's trafficking of women and young girls. They're:

Forced Marriage: In many parts of India, where there is a lower ratio of women to men due to female infanticide, girls and women are trafficked not only for prostitution but also for forced marriages. They are bought and sold like commodities and then forced into marriage.

Bonded Labor: Debt bondage is a widespread issue in our society, though not widely recognized, and it is illegal in India. According to the International Labour Organization, more than 11.7 million people in the Asia-Pacific region are in forced labor. Families facing financial hardships often sell their children into bonded labor. Both boys and girls are sold, typically working for years without pay. Victims of human trafficking are more likely to suffer from mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and other mental disorders. Women coerced into sexual trafficking are at a higher risk of HIV and other sexually transmitted infections.

Action Against the Guilty: The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act (ITPA) makes trafficking for commercial sexual exploitation illegal, with sentences of up to seven years in prison. Forced and bonded labor are also prohibited under the Juvenile Justice Act, the Child Labour Act, and the Bonded Labor Abolition Act. In response to the horrific December 2012 gang rape, the government introduced amendments to several laws related to sexual assault and sex trafficking. However, there remains a significant gap between the enactment and enforcement of these laws.

Crimes Related to Women Trafficking in India

Categories of Crimes Related to Human Trafficking

- **Importation of Girls from Foreign Countries (Sec. 366B IPC):** This law addresses the illegal importation of girls for exploitation.
- **Procuration of Minor Girls (Sec. 366-A IPC):** This section covers the procurement of minor girls for illegal purposes.
- **Buying of Minors for Prostitution (Sec. 373 IPC):** Previously referred to as buying girls for prostitution, this section deals with purchasing minors for sexual exploitation.
- **Selling of Minors for Prostitution (Sec. 372 IPC):** This section, which previously focused on selling girls for prostitution, now covers the selling of minors for sexual purposes.
- **Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956:** A key piece of legislation aimed at preventing trafficking for sexual exploitation.
- **HT-Human Trafficking (Sec. 370 & 370A IPC):** These sections were introduced following the enactment of the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, to address human trafficking comprehensively.

Laws Against Human Trafficking in India

India has several laws that address various forms of trafficking:

Indian Penal Code, 1860: The primary legislation in India that deals with human trafficking.

The important sections are as follows:

Section 347: Whoever wrongfully confines any person for the purpose of extorting from the person confined, or from any person interested in the person confined, any property or valuable security or of constraining the person confined or any person interested in such person to do anything illegal or to give any information which may facilitate the commission of an offence, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, and shall also be liable to fine.

Section 357: Whoever assaults or uses criminal force to any person, in attempting wrongfully to confine that person, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine which may extend to one thousand rupees or to both.

Section 363: Whoever kidnaps any person from India or from lawful guardianship, shall be punished with imprisonment of extension of seven years or may be liable to fine.

Section 365: **Kidnapping or Abduction for Confinement**

- Whoever kidnaps or abducts any person with the intent to cause that person to be secretly and wrongfully confined shall be punished with imprisonment for up to seven years and may also be fined.

Section 370: Definition of Trafficking of Persons: This section defines trafficking as any action taken for the purpose of exploitation, which includes:

- Recruiting,
- Transporting,
- Harboring,
- Transferring, or
- Receiving a person or persons,

by means of:

1. Using threats,
2. Using force or any other form of coercion,
3. Abduction,
4. Practicing fraud or deception,
5. Abuse of power, or
6. Inducement, including giving or receiving payments or benefits to obtain the consent of a person having control over the trafficked individual.

Penalties for Trafficking

- Anyone found guilty of trafficking will face rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of seven years, which may extend up to ten years, and may also be fined.
- If the trafficking offense involves more than one person, the punishment will be rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of ten years, which may extend to life imprisonment, and a fine.
- For trafficking involving a minor, the punishment is rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of ten years, which may extend to life imprisonment, and a fine.
- If the offense involves the trafficking of more than one minor, the punishment will be rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of fourteen years, which may extend to life imprisonment, and a fine.
- If a person is convicted of trafficking a minor more than once, they will be sentenced to life imprisonment, meaning imprisonment for the remainder of their natural life, and a fine.
- If a public servant or police officer is involved in trafficking, they will be sentenced to life imprisonment, meaning imprisonment for the remainder of their natural life, and a fine.
- Under Section 506, anyone committing the offense of criminal intimidation will be punished with imprisonment for up to two years, or with a fine, or both.

Special Provisions

Sex Trafficking

Section 354A: A man committing any of the following acts –

1. physical contact and advances involving unwelcome and explicit sexual overtures; or
2. a demand or request for sexual favours; or
3. showing pornography against the will of a woman; or
4. making sexually coloured remarks, shall be guilty of the offence of sexual harassment. shall be punished with rigorous imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

Section 376: Whoever commits rape, shall be punished with rigorous imprisonment of either description for a term which shall not be less than ten years, but which may extend to imprisonment for life, and shall also be liable to fine.

Forced Marriage

Section 366 (Kidnapping or Abduction of a Woman)-Anyone who kidnaps or abducts a woman with the intent to compel her, or knowing it is likely she will be compelled, to marry someone against her will, or to force or seduce her into illicit intercourse, shall be punished with imprisonment for a term that may extend up to ten years, and may also be fined.

Minor

Revised Legal Provisions

Section 366A: Anyone who induces a minor girl under eighteen to go from any place or to do any act with the intent that she may be, or knowing that it is likely she will be, forced or seduced into illicit intercourse with another person shall be punishable with imprisonment up to ten years and a fine.

Section 366B: Anyone who imports a girl under twenty-one years into India from any country outside India or from the State of Jammu and Kashmir, with the intent that she may be, or knowing it is likely that she will be, forced or seduced into illicit intercourse with another person shall be punishable with imprisonment up to ten years and a fine.

Section 370(4): If the trafficking offense involves a minor, the punishment shall be rigorous imprisonment for not less than ten years, which may extend to life imprisonment, and a fine.

Section 370(5): If the trafficking offense involves more than one minor, the punishment shall be rigorous imprisonment for not less than fourteen years, which may extend to life imprisonment, and a fine.

Section 370(6): If a person is convicted of trafficking a minor on more than one occasion, they shall be sentenced to life imprisonment, meaning imprisonment for the remainder of their natural life, and a fine.

Section 372: Anyone who sells, lets to hire, or otherwise disposes of any person under eighteen years with the intent that such person shall be employed or used for prostitution, illicit intercourse, or any unlawful and immoral purpose, or knowing it is likely that such person will be used for such purposes, shall be punishable with imprisonment up to ten years and a fine.

Slavery

Section 371: Whoever habitually imports, exports, removes, buys, sells traffics or deals in slaves, shall be punished with imprisonment for life, or with imprisonment of either description for a term not exceeding ten years, and shall also be liable to fine.

Section 374: Whoever unlawfully compels any person to labour against the will of that person, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine, or with both.

Aiding Human Trafficking

Section 368: Anyone who knowingly conceals or confines a person who has been kidnapped or abducted shall be punished as if they had kidnapped or abducted the person themselves, with the same intention, knowledge, or purpose as that with which they concealed or detained the person.

Section 370A: 1. "Anyone who knowingly, or having reason to believe, that a minor has been trafficked, engages such minor for sexual exploitation in any manner, shall be punished with rigorous imprisonment for a term not less than five years, which may extend to seven years, and shall also be liable to a fine." 2. "Anyone who knowingly, or having reason to believe, that a person has been trafficked, engages such person for sexual exploitation in any manner, shall be punished with

rigorous imprisonment for a term not less than three years, which may extend to five years, and shall also be liable to a fine."

(ii) IMMORAL TRAFFIC (PREVENTION) ACT 1956

This act deals with "human trafficking for the purpose of sexual exploitation".

Section 3: Operating a brothel is punishable by imprisonment for a term ranging from one to three years and a fine up to two thousand rupees.

Section 4: Living off the earnings of prostitution is punishable by imprisonment for a term of one to three years and a fine up to two thousand rupees. If the earnings involve a minor, the sentence ranges from seven to ten years in prison.

Section 5: Procuring, enticing, or taking a person for prostitution, with or without their consent, is punishable by imprisonment for a term of three to seven years and a fine up to two thousand rupees. If the act is against the person's will, the imprisonment term can extend from seven to fourteen years.

Section 6: If a person is found detained in a place where prostitution is practised, they will face imprisonment for a term ranging from seven to ten years, or possibly life imprisonment, and may also be fined.

In addition to the aforementioned, this Act also stipulates penalties for prostitution in or near public areas, seduction of an inmate, and seduction for the purpose of prostitution.

(iii) THE CONSTITUTION OF INDIA, 1949

Article 23: "Trafficking in humans and forced labour is prohibited and is punishable in accordance with law."

Article 24: "It states that any child under the age of fourteen years shall not work in any hazardous employment like factories or mines."

(iv) Trafficking of Person ("Prevention, Protection and Rehabilitation") Bill-2018 (Lapsed):

This bill, which was enacted on July 26, 2018, in the Lok Sabha, had the goals of stopping human trafficking, protecting and rehabilitating victims, and prosecuting offenders. It was also scheduled to be passed by the Rajya Sabha, but it has since expired. A number of particular laws have been passed in relation to the trafficking of women and children, including The Transplantation of Human Organs Act¹, The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act², The Bonded Labour System (Abolition) Act³, and The Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act⁴.

Role of the Non- Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

In the report "Trafficking in Women and Children in India" by Sen and Nair, NGOs are portrayed as being in a challenging position. Commercial sex survivors of exploitation were asked about their views on NGOs. Most expressed gratitude towards the NGO employees. However, when it came to the specific involvement of NGOs in human trafficking, a large portion of the victims were unaware of their role. Only a small percentage mentioned that NGOs were working to prevent HIV. Today, many NGOs, including "Human Rights Watch, Amnesty International, OXFAM, Save the Children, the Red Cross, Action Aid, and Shakti Vahini", are actively involved in combating trafficking. They promote human rights awareness and engage in social monitoring.

Trafficking And Human Rights

The debate on human rights remains surprisingly quiet on this urgent issue, which needs immediate attention and more careful consideration. The ITPA-1956 (Immoral Traffic Prevention Act of 1956),

later amended in 1986, did not include provisions for victim rights. It failed to offer adequate punishment for offenders and mishandled the crucial processes of rescuing and rehabilitating victims. Poorly maintained rehabilitation centres that lack proper medical and psychological care for traumatized victims often end up creating new victims. Additionally, India is severely affected due to widespread poverty and corruption. Human trafficking represents a severe violation of human rights and dignity, stripping victims of their freedoms, education, right to a dignified life, and other fundamental rights, effectively creating a modern form of slavery.

Human rights violations are rampant in brothels, where trafficked individuals, especially women and children, are forced into commercial sex work, embodying the ultimate human rights abuse. The survivors of this terrible trade are often powerless. When victims are detained, prosecuted, and convicted, the concept of rights becomes absurdly twisted, as measures meant to protect them instead become tools for further abuse. This dire situation demands urgent action through proper and effective legal measures.

Trafficking strikes at the core of our values concerning justice, morality, gender, and human rights, making it a contentious issue often written about with emotion rather than objectivity. It must be a top priority for academics, legal experts, and civil society members. A robust human rights system is crucial for any democracy, and it is essential to focus on both interpretation and reform, rather than delaying action.

Actions/ Initiatives by Mwcd

The Ministry of Women and Child Development (MWCD) has launched several programs in an effort to combat the trafficking of women and children.

- Mainstreaming and reintegrating trafficking victims was the goal of the 1998 National Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Women and Children.
- The Central Advisory Committee (CAB) was established to provide guidance on approaches and strategies for resolving the issue.
- Pre-rescue, rescue, and post-rescue protocols for child trafficking victims were developed as instructions for all parties involved in order to prevent commercial sexual exploitation.
- The Ministry of Home Affairs has established a specialized nodal cell tasked with supplying state governments with the information, studies, and research they require.
- All parties involved, including law enforcement and government officials, should get training to enhance their situational awareness and enable them to appropriately handle suspicious behaviour or individuals.
- For women in challenging situations, the MWCD manages Swadhar Homes and Short Stay Homes. MWCD has worked with the Ministry of External Affairs to establish special task teams aimed at stopping cross-border trafficking.

Methods and Strategies of Prevention

Many provisions in the UN Protocol aim to combat human trafficking. States are required to implement policies, initiatives, and safeguards to prevent human trafficking and protect victims from being re-trafficked. Victims endure immense suffering due to numerous rights violations, exacerbated by inequality, injustice, and exploitation by traffickers and others.

To address these issues, prevention policies, programs, and strategies must be specific and targeted towards the unique challenges faced. Prevention efforts must consider not only the source areas but also demand regions, transit points, and trafficking routes, tailoring strategies to the needs of targeted groups and specific circumstances.

Combining prosecution, protection, and prevention is the most effective approach. Prosecution involves identifying and apprehending traffickers and confiscating their illegal assets. Protection

encompasses all actions taken to address victims' complaints, aiding in their survival, rehabilitation, and reintegration. Together, prosecution and protection contribute to prevention.

Efforts should focus on alleviating poverty, illiteracy, and related issues to provide better livelihood options. Specific support packages should be available for women and children in vulnerable communities where commercial sexual exploitation might be seen as the only option. Education and other services should empower at-risk populations by enhancing their capacities.

Patriarchal attitudes and gender discrimination significantly contribute to the vulnerability of women and girls, leading to serious rights violations such as high rates of infanticide, female foeticide, and discrimination in workplaces, healthcare, and education. Prevention strategies must address these risk factors.

Natural and man-made disasters increase vulnerability, necessitating relief and aftercare programs that focus on women's and children's rights. At the local level, law enforcement and NGOs must work together to combat human trafficking in source areas. Public awareness campaigns and community engagement are crucial components of prevention, with community policing being particularly effective.

Combating human trafficking requires political will. Raising legal awareness is essential for any social action program, as genuine social progress cannot occur without it. Empowered individuals who know their rights can develop zero tolerance for abuse and exploitation.

Immigration officials at borders need to be sensitized to collaborate with law enforcement and NGOs in combating human trafficking. Help booths and hotlines are vital for providing immediate assistance to those in need. The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment is considering partnering with NGOs and government agencies to establish support booths and hotlines, connecting police helplines, missing person bureaus, child rights NGOs, and child lines across India to create a powerful tool against human trafficking.

Landmark Judgements on Trafficking of Human In India

People's Union for Democratic Rights v. Union of India

In this case, the Supreme Court of India defined forced labor under Article-23 of the Indian Constitution. The court explained that "force" includes not only legal and physical coercion but also economic pressure that leaves an individual with no other choice but to work or provide services, even if the payment is below the minimum wage.

M C Mehta Vs State Of Tamil Nadu

In this Public Interest Litigation, the Supreme Court detailed measures to support families and victims of child labor. The court ruled that employers who violate the Act should pay a compensation of Rs 20,000 for each child employed illegally. Inspectors appointed under Section 17 of the Act are responsible for enforcing this provision.

The collected fines would be deposited into a fund named the Child Labor Rehabilitation-cum-Welfare Fund. This fund could be managed at the district or area level, ensuring that even if the child is dismissed from employment, the employer's liability remains. The fund's income would be used exclusively to support the affected child. To maximize revenue, the funds could be placed in high-yield accounts at nationalized banks or other financial institutions.

Conclusion

The protection of human rights under the Indian Constitution is well-founded, with numerous international treaties and human rights covenants bolstering these rights. Courts in India have expanded the human rights provisions in the Constitution, drawing on these international agreements. Consequently, many human rights violations recognized in international treaties can also be addressed through the Indian legal system. However, this legal framework must be supported by services, a fundamental change in family and societal values, and accurate social perceptions. Trafficking of women gravely violates their rights, compromising their security and dignity. While the Indian Constitution guarantees equal rights for men and women, these guarantees often fall short

in practice. To effectively enforce anti-trafficking laws and protect the rights of women and other vulnerable groups, the government must demonstrate strong political will. Crimes like trafficking, which can escalate into widespread societal evils, require decisive action and strict policies. Prompt action is essential; delaying will make it increasingly difficult to address the issue.

References

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- ¹ Transplantation of Human Organs Act of 1994
 - ² The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act of 2006
 - ³ The Bonded Labour System (Abolition) Act of 1976
 - ⁴ and The Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act of 1986

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